

Acknowledgement

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Synthesis of 5-Mercapto-4-Amino-3-Substituted-1,2,4-Triazoles and Their Mono- and Disulphide Derivatives

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TRIAZOLES and their derivatives have been proved to be effective bactericides¹, pesticides² and fungicides^{3,4}. They have been used in the gravimetric estimations of silver, copper and lead⁵⁻⁸. In this communication we report a few new derivatives of triazoles.

The compounds IIa-d (Table 1) are prepared according to the known method⁹. They are characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectra. These compounds on oxidation with thionylchloride and bromine in absolute ethanol, respectively yield monosulfides (IIIa-d) and disulphides (IVa-d). The compounds Va-f are prepared in 4*N* HCl and oxidised to their respective sulphides (VIa-d) and disulphides (VIIa-d)².

TABLE 1—3-SUBSTITUTED-4-AMINO-5-MERCAPTO-1,2,4-TRIAZOLES (IIa-d AND Va-f)

Compd. R/R' no.	R/R'	M.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	S
IIa	H	108	20.15 (20.69)	3.51 (3.45)	48.00 (48.28)	27.72 (27.59)
IIb	CH ₃	218-19	26.23 (27.69)	4.65 (4.62)	42.81 (43.08)	24.47 (24.62)
IIc	C ₂ H ₅	140-41	33.00 (33.38)	5.64 (5.56)	38.79 (38.89)	22.30 (22.22)
IId	C ₃ H ₇	72-74	38.45 (37.97)	4.95 (6.33)	48.01 (35.44)	21.87 (20.25)
Va	C ₆ H ₅	234	48.57 (50.00)	4.02 (4.17)	28.78 (29.17)	16.52 (16.66)
Vb	<i>o</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄	228-90	46.18 (46.16)	3.60 (3.35)	26.59 (26.92)	15.45 (15.38)
Vc	<i>o</i> -H ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	242	46.35 (46.88)	4.75 (4.83)	33.70 (33.82)	15.08 (15.46)
Vd	<i>p</i> -H ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	290	46.30 (46.38)	4.80 (4.83)	33.61 (33.82)	15.45 (15.46)
Ve	CH ₂ ON	241-42	30.55 (30.96)	3.19 (3.23)	45.00 (45.16)	20.41 (20.65)
Vf	CH ₂ NH ₂	250-51	24.80 (24.82)	4.78 (4.83)	48.25 (48.27)	22.00 (22.07)

The synthetic route for these compounds is shown below.

Infrared spectra: All the triazoles exhibit a medium to high intensity band in the 1660-1610 cm^{-1} region attributable to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. The band due to ν_{NH} associated with the thione form appears in the 3330-3225 and 3200-3150 cm^{-1} regions. The ν_{SH} appears in the region 2600-2500 cm^{-1} . For compounds Ve $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ appears at 2200 cm^{-1} .

TABLE 2—BIS(4-AMINO-3-SUBSTITUTED-1,2,4-TRIAZOLE-5-YL)MONO (IIIa-d AND VIa-d) AND DI (IVa-d AND VIIa-d) SULPHIDES

Compd. no.	R'	X	M.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	S
IIIa	H	S	110-12	29.78 (24.24)	3.00 (3.03)	56.05 (56.57)	15.98 (16.16)
IIIb	OH ₂	S	251	31.00 (31.86)	4.31 (4.42)	49.50 (49.56)	14.01 (14.16)
IIIc	C ₂ H ₅	S	255-56	37.25 (37.80)	5.97 (5.51)	44.13 (44.09)	12.61 (12.51)
IIId	C ₆ H ₇	S	191-92	43.00 (42.55)	6.41 (6.98)	39.53 (39.72)	10.85 (11.35)
VIa	C ₆ H ₅	S	78	55.70 (54.86)	4.08 (4.00)	32.00 (32.00)	9.21 (9.14)
VIb	<i>o</i> -HO-C ₆ H ₄	S	253-55	50.00 (50.26)	3.73 (3.66)	29.48 (29.32)	8.51 (8.98)
VIc	<i>o</i> -H ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	S	250	50.12 (50.53)	4.16 (4.21)	36.80 (36.84)	8.33 (8.42)
VIId	<i>p</i> -H ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	S	116-18	50.53 (50.53)	4.11 (4.21)	36.96 (36.84)	8.34 (8.42)
IVa	H	S-S	185-38	20.57 (20.87)	2.59 (2.61)	48.50 (48.70)	27.77 (27.89)
IVb	OH ₂	S-S	155	27.02 (27.91)	3.90 (3.88)	42.78 (43.41)	23.95 (24.81)
IVc	C ₂ H ₅	S-S	185	33.56 (33.57)	4.81 (4.90)	39.00 (39.16)	22.71 (22.38)
IVd	C ₆ H ₇	S-S	115-16	38.51 (38.22)	5.74 (5.73)	35.23 (35.67)	20.00 (20.38)
VIIa	C ₆ H ₅	S-S	85	49.76 (50.26)	3.60 (3.66)	29.00 (29.32)	16.89 (16.75)
VIIb	<i>o</i> -HO-C ₆ H ₄	S-S	196-98	46.30 (46.38)	3.74 (3.38)	28.75 (27.05)	15.35 (15.46)
VIIc	<i>o</i> -H ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	S-S	198-200	46.50 (46.60)	3.72 (3.88)	33.03 (33.98)	15.50 (15.53)
VIIId	<i>p</i> -H ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	S-S	145-46	46.14 (46.60)	3.78 (3.88)	32.89 (33.98)	15.96 (15.53)

Biological activity : All the reported compounds have been evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. Almost all the mercaptotriazoles (IIa-d ; Va-f) are found to be more active against *S. aureus* than their mono- and disulphide. The compound VI has shown better activity (15 mm) than the others. VIa has exhibited the highest inhibition (18 mm) against gram -ve organism *E. coli*. The others which have shown moderate activity against *E. coli* are IIIb-d, IVc and IVd.

Experimental

The m.ps. are uncorrected. The ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin Elmer-297 spectrophotometer.

Thiocarbohydrazide (I) was prepared by the known method¹⁰. The compounds IIa-d were prepared according to the method reported⁹.

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